

Searches for new physics in CMS in events with jets, leptons and photons in the final state

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Abstract

Many new physics models, e.g., compositeness, extra dimensions, extended Higgs sectors, supersymmetric theories, and dark sector extensions, are expected to manifest themselves in final states with jets, leptons, and photons. This talk presents searches in CMS for new phenomena in these final states, focusing on the recent results obtained using the full Run 2 data set collected at the LHC.

1 Introduction

The standard model (SM) of particle physics has been extremely successful at describing fundamental particles and their interactions over its approximately five decade lifetime. Despite its success, however, it is not a complete theory, leading to the proposal of a huge variety of models for beyond the SM (BSM) physics, with a huge number of these having been explored at the LHC. In this talk, we will summarize results from the most recent searches from CMS [1] in events with jets, leptons, and photons in the final state. All of these searches use data from Run 2 of the LHC with $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV, and all but one use the full data set of 138 fb^{-1} .

2 Nonresonant searches

2.1 τ lepton + missing momentum

The first search is for events with a hadronically decaying τ lepton (τ_h) and high missing transverse momentum (p_T^{miss}) in the final state [3]. The benchmark model for this search is a heavy charged vector boson, W' , decaying via $W' \rightarrow \tau\nu$. The search is done using events collected with triggers that require at least one τ_h or high p_T^{miss} . Offline, $p_T^{\text{miss}} > 200$ GeV is required, and the high- p_T τ_h is identified with the DeepTau ID.

The transverse mass (m_T), calculated from the p_T of the τ_h and the p_T^{miss} , is used as the main discriminating variable. This variable is shown in Fig. 1 (left) for both data and simulation. The main irreducible background is W + jets, while jets misidentified as τ_h are also a significant background. The misidentification rate for the latter is estimated from a signal-free control region in data, and all other backgrounds are estimated from simulation.

Figure 1: Left: the distribution of the transverse mass, calculated from the p_T of the τ_h and the p_T^{miss} . The ratio of background-subtracted data to background yields is shown in the bottom panel. Right: upper limits on the coupling ratio $g_{W'}/g_W$ as a function of $m_{W'}$ [3].

The data agree well with the estimated backgrounds, and limits are placed on the coupling ratio of W' and W ($g_{W'}/g_W$) versus $m_{W'}$ (see Fig. 1 (right)). In the special case of the sequential SM (SSM), where $g_{W'} = g_W$, the W' is excluded up to a mass of 4.8 TeV. The results are also interpreted within a wide range of other models.

2.2 Composite Majorana neutrino

Composite fermions are one possibility for BSM physics, where the usual SM particles are composed of more fundamental particles called preons. The next search looks for excited neutrino

states (N_ℓ) produced in association with a charged lepton of the same flavor and decaying via $N_\ell \rightarrow q\bar{q}'$ [4]. Events are collected with single-electron and single-muon triggers, and at least two high- p_T leptons of the same flavor are required offline. In addition, a large-radius jet (J) with $p_T > 190$ GeV is required.

The main discriminating variable is $m(\ell\ell J)$. This variable, which is shown in Fig. 2 for data and simulation, is related to the N_ℓ mass, and generally peaks at $m(\ell\ell J) > m(N_\ell)$. Background estimates are taken from simulation, and the shape of $m(\ell\ell J)$ for Drell-Yan, which is the dominant background source, is corrected using scale factors calculated from data. In addition, Drell-Yan and top quark control regions are included in the fit to data in order to constrain these backgrounds.

Figure 2: The distribution of $m(eeJ)$ (left) and $m(\mu\mu J)$ (right). The middle panel shows the ratio of data to post-fit and pre-fit background yields, and the bottom panel shows the pulls [4].

No significant excess is observed in the data, and limits are placed on the compositeness scale (Λ) versus $m(N_\ell)$ (see Fig. 3). For masses equal to the compositeness scale, N_e (N_μ) are excluded up to 6.0 (6.1) TeV. This represents an improvement in the limits on this class of resonances by more than 1 TeV.

Figure 3: Lower limits on the compositeness scale, Λ , versus $m(N_e)$ (left) and $m(N_\mu)$ (right) [4].

3 Resonant searches

3.1 γ -jet resonance

The next search is for resonances in the γ -jet final state [6]. Two benchmark models are explored by this search: excited states of quarks and quantum black holes (QBH). This search is done using events collected with single- γ triggers, and offline, a high- p_T γ is required, as well as a wide jet with $p_T > 170$ GeV. The wide jet is constructed by clustering narrow jets within $\Delta R < 1.1$.

The invariant mass of the highest- p_T γ and highest- p_T wide jet ($m_{\gamma+\text{jet}}$) is used as the main discriminating variable and is shown in Fig. 4 (left) for data and simulated signal. No evidence for a resonance is observed, and limits are placed on excited quark models, both light and heavy flavors (see Fig. 4 (right)), and two varieties of QBH models.

Figure 4: Left: the distribution of $m_{\gamma+\text{jet}}$. The lower panel shows the difference between data and the fit divided by the statistical uncertainty in data. Right: lower limits on the SM couplings for the excited quark models versus the resonance mass [6].

3.2 GeV-scale dimuon resonance

Next is a search for low-mass resonances decaying to two oppositely charged muons, with such resonances potentially acting as a portal between SM fields and an unknown dark sector [5]. The trigger strategy for this search is unique in that it uses high-rate “scouting” triggers that require two muons with $p_T > 3$ GeV. This is a much lower p_T threshold than more conventional triggers and is achieved by reading out less data per event in order to control the data rate. The trigger efficiency is shown in Fig. 5 for data collected in 2017 and 2018. Offline, two prompt, oppositely charged muons are required, with an MVA used to select well-reconstructed muons.

The dimuon invariant mass, $m_{\mu\mu}$, is used as the main discriminating variable, with the region around the J/ψ and $\psi(2S)$ peaks being excluded. In addition to the inclusive selection described above, a high- p_T selection is defined where the p_T of the dimuon system is required to be above 35 GeV (20 GeV) for $m_{\mu\mu}$ below (above) the excluded mass region. An excess in the high- p_T selection is observed at 2.41 GeV with a local (global) significance of 3.2 (3.1) σ . This is reflected in the model-independent limits shown in Fig. 6, and coincides with a 3.1- σ excess observed by LHCb in a comparable analysis [7]. Limits are also placed on the parameters of two specific models: a dark photon model and a two Higgs doublet model with an extra scalar.

3.3 Associated production of dilepton resonance

The final search is for a dilepton scalar or pseudoscalar resonance (ϕ) produced in association with a W or Z boson or a top quark pair, where at least one of the associated particles decays

Figure 5: Trigger efficiencies for the scouting triggers used in [5] for the 2017 (left) and 2018 (right) data. The efficiencies are shown as a function of $m_{\mu\mu}$ and the angular separation between the two muons ($\Delta R_{\mu\mu}$) [5].

Figure 6: Upper limits on the production of dimuon resonances as a function of $m_{\mu\mu}$ for the inclusive (left) and high- p_T (right) selections [5].

leptonically [2]. This search is done using events collected with single-electron or single-muon triggers, and offline, seven channels are defined, depending on the number of light leptons and τ_h in the final state:

- 4 leptons: 1–4 light leptons, 0–3 τ_h
- 3 leptons: 1–3 light leptons, 0–2 τ_h

The same-flavor dilepton mass is used as the main discriminating variable, excluding the region near the mass of the Z boson. Separate signal regions are defined above and below the Z boson mass, resulting in 36 signal regions altogether, depending on the targeted production and decay modes.

Two types of background are important for this search: real leptons produced promptly or from conversions and fake leptons. The former are estimated from simulation, with normalizations and corrections derived from dedicated control regions in data. The latter is estimated from lepton isolation sidebands in data. The largest excess is seen in the high-mass $Z\phi(ee)$ region at 156 GeV and has a local (global) significance of 2.9 (1.4) σ (see plot of M_{ee} in Fig. 7 (left)). Limits are placed on scalar, pseudoscalar, and Higgs-like signal models, an example of which is shown in Fig. 7 (right).

Figure 7: Left: dielectron mass spectrum for the high-mass $Z\phi(ee)$ signal region. The lower panel shows the ratio of the data to the expected background yields. Right: upper limits on the production of a Higgs-like ϕ versus the ϕ mass [2].

4 Conclusion

CMS has a broad program searching for beyond the standard model physics in whatever form it may take. Here we have seen a selection of recent results from searches in events with jets, leptons, and photons in the final state. At this point, no statistically significant excess has been seen. We are currently in the middle of Run 3 of the LHC, with about 65fb^{-1} collected so far at $\sqrt{s} = 13.6\text{ TeV}$, with even more data being recorded and analyzed now. New and updated results will be coming soon, hopefully including some exciting discoveries.

References

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